

Aim- Turbidity-based titrations for the PN-PLL system with different PN concentrations

- **Materials and methods:** poly-L-lysine (Sigma Aldrich, average Mw=22500), pyranin (Carl Roth), MQ water
- **Sample preparation-** 100 mM PN stock in MQ water was diluted to 0.5, 1, 3, and 6 mM solutions; PLL stock solutions was prepared (5 mM). Appropriate amounts were added to achieve a range of PLL concentrations (0-80 μ M). The dilution was kept below 5%.
- **Instrumentation-**
 1. Microplate reader assays. OD600 endpoint absorbance measurements were performed at 620 nm on a Byonoy Absorbance 96-well microplate reader using Greiner transparent 96-well plates with a flat bottom. (Byonoy Absorbance 96 software app).
- **Observations and conclusions:**

The measured absorbance (A) was processed into turbidity as: % Turbidity $100 - 100 \cdot 10^{-A}$

Calculated values are shown as a heat map. The increase in turbidity was substantial for 6 and 3 mM PN solutions (up to 80%). In a 1 mM PN solution, a slight increase in turbidity was observed; meanwhile, in a 0.5 mM solution, the turbidity remained constant. The table shows the added volume of the stock and measured A values.

PLL (μ M)	V μ l (5 mM PLL)	Absorbance measured			
		0.5 mM PN	1 mM PN	3 mM PN	6 mM PN
0	0	0.045	0.049	0.071	0.063
1	0.1	0.055	0.15	0.13	0.162
5	0.5	0.066	0.303	0.222	0.239
15	1.5	0.054	0.121	0.448	0.442
30	3	0.065	0.049	0.695	0.666
40	4	0.055	0.051	0.725	0.729
60	6	0.066	0.052	0.501	0.894
80	8	0.058	0.048	0.105	0.909

• **Data available at:**

"W:\AKDhiman\Team\Minea Kapidzic\Turbidity measurements\22092025_M-ET-06"

Relevant for the manuscript Figure 1 (a).

Attached files

map.png

sha256: de0936ddc548a64da9b5bc0bae0ded61f970e27e750a21f3efa57729677a0a30

Table for heat map.png

sha256: 791f73c4ceddd281774b9739e3ca25ebbef7de6d7ca903f6170f9a8247c8c72e

PLL concentration (μM)	PN concentration (mM)	Value
0	0.5	9.800
0	1	9.800
0	3	9.800
0	6	9.800
10	0.5	25.40
10	1	25.40
10	3	25.40
10	6	25.40
20	0.5	41.00
20	1	41.00
20	3	41.00
20	6	41.00
30	0.5	56.60
30	1	56.60
30	3	56.60
30	6	56.60
40	0.5	72.20
40	1	72.20
40	3	72.20
40	6	72.20
50	0.5	87.80
50	1	87.80
50	3	87.80
50	6	87.80
60	0.5	87.80
60	1	87.80
60	3	87.80
60	6	87.80
70	0.5	87.80
70	1	87.80
70	3	87.80
70	6	87.80
80	0.5	87.80
80	1	87.80
80	3	87.80
80	6	87.80

Unique eLabID: 20251106-da0d4a00bf57229e6c109b40f37bb45b67af473d
 Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=9123>

Aim- Triplicates of turbidity-based titrations for the PN-PLL system with different PN concentrations

- **Materials and methods:** poly-L-lysine (Sigma Aldrich, average Mw=22500), pyranin (Carl Roth), MQ water
- **Sample preparation-** 100 mM PN stock in MQ water was diluted to 0.5, 1, 3, and 6 mM solutions; PLL stock solutions were prepared (1, 2, and 5 mM). Appropriate amounts were added to achieve a range of PLL concentrations (0-80 μ M). The dilution was kept below 5%.
- **Instrumentation-**
 1. Microplate reader assays. OD600 endpoint absorbance measurements were performed at 620 nm on a Byonoy Absorbance 96-well microplate reader using Greiner transparent 96-well plates with a flat bottom. (Byonoy Absorbance 96 software app).
- **Observations and conclusions:**

The measured absorbance (A) was processed into turbidity as: % Turbidity $100 - 100 \cdot 10^{-A}$.

Observations and conclusions:

"W:\AKDhiman\Team\Minea Kapidzic\Turbidity measurements\17102025_M-ET-07"

Relevant for the manuscript Figure S1.

Attached files

6mM PN.png

sha256: baa6af7abeb3f843b24b27e20b76092d1afccf963d054c5c1eba6757a3a96af0

3mM PN.png

sha256: 50d237920e57a27371997375fe6f1988ef8d544f35a98800f36d8059d6701440

1 mM PN.png

sha256: bf3498acf3671057e6b293bdd83a838ff4bcec8932178cf98f5e4689be4a4bf4

0.5 mM PN.png

sha256: c09e6998f10125c70ed19aba07f390647c5cca264598364f24be172c1bdb3cbe

Unique eLabID: 20251106-c6109266ff659c069b819c6fb2009ff05f582f0d
Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=9126>

Aim- Control experiment: Turbidity measurements with Sulforhodamine

- **Materials and methods:** poly-L-lysine (Sigma Aldrich, average Mw=22500), pyranin (Carl Roth), Sulforhodamine B (Sigma Aldrich), MQ water
- **Sample preparation-** A 3 mM solution was prepared. In different vials, increasing concentrations of SRh stock were added (50 mM). The absorbance was measured for a concentration range of 0-10 mol% relative to PN. PLL was added to induce coacervation (40 μ M).
- **Instrumentation-**
 1. Microplate reader assays. OD600 endpoint absorbance measurements were performed at 620 nm on a Byonoy Absorbance 96-well microplate reader using Greiner transparent 96-well plates with a flat bottom. (Byonoy Absorbance 96 software app).
- **Observations and conclusions:**

The measured absorbance (A) was processed into turbidity as: % Turbidity $100 - 100 \cdot 10^{-A}$. The results are presented in the plot below.

Increasing concentration of encapsulated SRh did not significantly affect the turbidity of the system.

- **Data available at:**

"W:\AKDhiman\Team\Minea Kapidzic\Turbidity measurements\30092025_M-ET-08"

Relevant for the manuscript Figure S12.

Attached file

Turbidity, control.png

sha256: 066e7101be9abeb83535aecdd86b182dc54c0be7690c2deb2ab62c68334d06579

Unique eLabID: 20251106-ceda8a4dd88f9524f0c1cf9eb48707faa0df29d0

Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=9127>

Aim- Turbidity-based titrations for the SRh-PLL system with different SRh concentrations

- **Materials and methods:** poly-L-lysine (Sigma Aldrich, average Mw=22500), Sulforhodamine B (Sigma Aldrich), MQ water
- **Sample preparation:** SRh solutions were prepared from a stock solution (50 mM, concentrations: 0.03, 0.06, 0.09, 0.12, and 0.15 mM). Appropriate amounts were added to achieve a range of PLL concentrations (0-40 μ M). The dilution was kept below 5%.
- **Instrumentation-**
 1. Microplate reader assays. OD600 endpoint absorbance measurements were performed at 620 nm on a Byonoy Absorbance 96-well microplate reader using Greiner transparent 96-well plates with a flat bottom. (Byonoy Absorbance 96 software app).
- **Observations and conclusions:**

The measured absorbance (A) was processed into turbidity as: % Turbidity $100 - 100 \cdot 10^{-A}$.

The data is presented in the heatmap. An increase in PLL concentration did not result in a significant increase in turbidity for any SRh concentration.

- **Data available at:**

"W:\AKDhiman\Team\Minea Kapidzic\Turbidity measurements\16102025_M-ET-09"

Relevant for the manuscript Figure 1 (e).

Attached file

SRh heat map.png

sha256: 3625d99b136864b9fc332041ee0e43b44f98d7f44016a55c5e02c7d1835f2a8a

Unique eLabID: 20251106-b2837de5d2f57c2209975af75cd39a064dd3fff4

Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=9128>

Aim- Fluorescence-based titrations of a PN solution

- **Materials and methods:** poly-L-lysine (Sigma Aldrich, average Mw=22500), pyranin (Carl Roth), MQ water
- **Sample preparation-** 50 mM PN stock in MQ water was diluted to 3 mM solutions. PLL stock solution was prepared (5 mM). Appropriate amounts were added to achieve a range of PLL concentrations (0-80 μ M). The dilution was kept below 5%.
- **Instrumentation-**
 1. Spectra were recorded on a JASCO FP-800 fluorescence spectrometer. Samples were prepared as stated and measured in Quartz cuvettes (500 μ L Hellma Analytics) with a path length of 10x2 mm. The sample was excited at λ_{ex} = 458 nm, and the emission spectrum was recorded at λ_{em} = 478- 750 nm.

- **Observations and conclusions:**

Upon the increase of PLL concentration, PN intensity gets quenched.

- **Data available at:**

"W:\AKDhiman\Team\Minea Kapidzic\Fluorescent spectroscopy\10092025_M-ET-11"

Relevant for the manuscript Figure 1 (b).

Attached file

titration.png

sha256: 10d2da5ad3c548b16b0c9ca9c43842e1b396649e1c9b1b1f3e580e56a42bc859

Unique eLabID: 20251106-d9b4aa8013f1d95408028d125fbe3771831f9942

Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=9129>

Aim- Fluorescence spectrum of PLL-ATP coacervates encapsulating different concentrations of SRh

- **Materials and methods:** poly-L-lysine (Sigma Aldrich, average $M_w=22500$), adenosine triphosphate (ATP) (Carl Roth), Sulforhodamine B (Sigma Aldrich), MQ water
- **Sample preparation:** 50 mM SRh stock in MQ water was diluted to different concentrations (0.03, 0.06, 0.09, 0.12, and 0.15 mM). PLL stock solution was prepared (5 mM). ATP stock was prepared in MQ water, and pH was adjusted to 7.01. To each SRh solution, ATP (5 mM) and PLL (15 μM) were added.
- **Instrumentation-**
 1. Spectra were recorded on a JASCO FP-800 fluorescence spectrometer. Samples were prepared as stated and measured in Quartz cuvettes (500 μL Hellma Analytics) with a path length of 10 \times 2 mm. The sample was excited at a wavelength of direct excitation of SRh ($\lambda_{\text{ex}}= 561 \text{ nm}$) and the emission spectrum was recorded at $\lambda_{\text{em}}= 571- 750 \text{ nm}$.

- **Observations and conclusions:**

In ATP-PLL coacervates, as SRh concentration increases, fluorescence gets quenched.

- **Data available at:**

"W:\AKDhiman\Team\Minea Kapidzic\Fluorescent spectroscopy\29102025_M-ET-12"

Relevant for the manuscript Figure 1(f).

Attached file

SRh ATP-PLL.png

sha256: dfa277510154396d0028e1d829077732e946ef409c22dd725f81f2de2d0f831d

Unique eLabID: 20251106-f546e9573cea026785077be8e5f48bb684f4792c

Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=9130>

Aim- Fluorescence spectrum of PN and SRh

- **Materials and methods:** pyranin (Carl Roth), Sulforhodamine B (Sigma Aldrich), MQ water
- **Sample preparation:** A 3 mM PN solution was prepared from a 100 mM PN stock and a 0.03 mM SRh from a 5 mM stock in MQ.
- **Instrumentation-**
 1. Spectra were recorded on a JASCO FP-800 fluorescence spectrometer. Samples were prepared as stated and measured in Quartz cuvettes (500 μ L Hellma Analytics) with a path length of 10 \times 2 mm. Solutions were excited at λ_{ex} = 458 nm, and the emission spectra were recorded at λ_{em} = 478- 750 nm. Additionally, excitation spectra were recorded (λ_{em} =511 nm for PN and λ_{em} =585 nm for SRh)
- **Observations and conclusions:**

- **Data available at:**

"W:\AKDhiman\Team\Minea Kapidzic\Fluorescent spectroscopy\11092025_M-ET-13"

Relevant for manuscript Figure S10

Attached file

exci_emiss.png

sha256: 1125a2ceff830cb723b252c00ed07a26e06060872112542fe765c720df665b42

Unique eLabID: 20251106-182de97e85cb6ef26be8f53a2a5e3a462de71db2

Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=9134>

Aim: UV-Vis spectrum of PN and SRh

- **Materials and methods:** pyranin (Carl Roth), Sulforhodamine B (Sigma Aldrich), MQ water
- **Sample preparation:** A 0.3 mM PN solution was prepared from a 100 mM PN stock and a 0.3 mM SRh from a 5 mM stock in MQ.

- **Instrumentation:**

1. UV-Vis spectra were recorded using a JASCO V-750 spectrometer in Quartz cuvettes (Hellma) with a 2 mm path length. The measurements were performed with a scan speed of 200 nm/min and a data interval of 1 nm.

- **Observations and conclusions:**

- **Data available at:**

"W:\AKDhiman\Team\Minea Kapidzic\UV\09102025_M-ET-14"

Relevant for manuscript Figure S10

Attached file

UV.png

sha256: 163a53c911c407eed1c113161518a7c4995110c3d5780de464ff0f9b399bdb8

Unique eLabID: 20251107-95b29a357265069596cffa366ed625e27693c900
Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=9140>

Aim: Zeta potential measurements of PN-PLL coacervates with different SRh concentrations

- **Materials and methods:** poly-L-lysine (Sigma Aldrich, average Mw=22500), pyranin (Carl Roth), Sulforhodamine B (Sigma Aldrich), Cy5, MQ water
- **Sample preparation:** As described in M-ET-08
- **Instrumentation-**
 1. Zeta potential and size measurements were performed on a Malvern Zetasizer Advance equipped with a maximum 10 mW He-Ne laser, emitting at 633 nm. Malvern disposable polycarbonate folded capillary cells with gold-plated beryllium-copper electrodes (DTS1070), which were rinsed with ethanol and MQ water before filling, were used. All measurements were at 25 °C, and the sample's temperature was allowed to equilibrate for 120 seconds.
 2. CLSM- imaging was done with different SRh concentrations. Excitation wavelength λ_{ex} = 633 nm (Cy5)
- **Observations and conclusions:**

The average zeta potential values measured for PN-PLL coacervates with increasing SRh concentration are presented in the table. The variations of measured potential across SRh concentrations are negligible, which suggests that encapsulation of the SRh does not disturb the coacervate microenvironment. SRh concentration does not affect coacervate size significantly. The values obtained from DLS and CLSM were in agreement.

SRh (mM)	ζ (mV)
0	7.229 ± 0.025
0.03	6.787 ± 0.595
0.15	8.41 ± 0.369

SRh (mM)	d_{avg} CLSM (μm)	d_{avg} DLS (μm)
0	2.9	2.8
0.03	2.7	2.5
0.15	2.3	2.9

0 mM SRh

0.03 mM SRh

0.15 mM SRh

• **Data available at:**

"W:\AKDhiman\Team\Minea Kapidzic\Zetapotential\21102025_M-ET-15"

Relevant for the manuscript Table S1, Table S2

Attached files

image.png

sha256: 0dc52a17395e7c58eed194a2c12c53c74c6bfe9bbddff39af63d9cdcaf7c6cf0

image.png

sha256: fee7fc4c430425aeab24f056dd88817853907f4bd156157d812a8fbc6eab4da4

SRh (mM)	d_{avg} (nm)	d_{avg} (μm)
0	2.9	2.9
0.03	2.7	2.7
0.15	2.3	2.3

zeta.png

sha256: 5305a3558259684545e6961d5fcf5991eaa7f45273adacf9810ecad088d39d67

SRh (mM)	ζ (mV)
0	7.229 ± 0.025
0.03	6.787 ± 0.595
0.15	6.41 ± 0.369

Unique eLabID: 20251107-8999329a841116507702c80423a5f076a20738d1
Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=9142>

Aim: Energy transfer experiment via fluorescent spectroscopy

- **Materials and methods:** poly-L-lysine (Sigma Aldrich, average Mw=22500), pyranine (Carl Roth), Sulforhodamine B (Sigma Aldrich), MQ water
- **Sample preparation:** 50 mM SRh stock in MQ water was diluted to different concentrations (0-20 mol% relative to PN). PLL stock solution was prepared (5 mM). To each SRh solution, PN (3 mM) and PLL (40 μ M) were added. For all experiments, PLL was added in increments (0.5, 0.5, 1, 1, 1 μ l).
- **Instrumentation-**
 1. Spectra were recorded on a JASCO FP-800 fluorescence spectrometer. Samples were prepared as stated and measured in Quartz cuvettes (500 μ L Hellma Analytics) with a path length of 10 \times 2 mm. The sample was excited at λ_{ex} = 458 nm, and the emission spectrum was recorded at λ_{em} = 478- 750 nm.
- **Observations and conclusions:**

As SRh concentration increases, the intensity of the PN peak decreases. At 5 % and 10 %, it further shifts to higher wavelengths and increases in intensity. Before the 2 % and 20 % measurements, the device was turned off for maintenance, resulting in the spectra not following the intensity trends of the previous measurements.

Data available at:

"W:\AKDhiman\Team\Minea Kapidzic\Fluorescent spectroscopy\23092025_M-ET-16"

Relevant for the manuscript Figure S14.

Attached files

graph 3.png

sha256: c0d848236711cf0cce6da22e6e3d3871841a3129fb835766c5efea985e208cd7

graph 2.png

sha256: dd4868c736684dc23c32cecd3ef16fe827d4d70fa0f7b563da06ec03afe678cc

Unique eLabID: 20251109-97073561ddfb7d1520e3956c18ca33b7e40b0606

Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=9152>

Aim: Energy transfer experiment via fluorescent spectroscopy (solution and coacervate state)

- **Materials and methods:** poly-L-lysine (Sigma Aldrich, average Mw=22500), pyranine (Carl Roth), Sulforhodamine B (Sigma Aldrich), MQ water
- **Sample preparation:** 50 mM SRh stock in MQ water was diluted to different concentrations (0.03, 0.06, 0.09, 0.12, and 0.15 mM). PLL stock solution was prepared (5 mM). To each SRh solution, PN (3 mM) and PLL (40 μ M) were added. The spectra were recorded before (solution) and after (coacervate) the addition of PLL. For all experiments, PLL was added in increments (0.5, 0.5, 1, 1, 1 μ l).
- **Instrumentation-**
 1. Spectra were recorded on a JASCO FP-800 fluorescence spectrometer. Samples were prepared as stated and measured in Quartz cuvettes (500 μ L Hellma Analytics) with a path length of 10 \times 2 mm. The sample was excited at λ_{ex} = 458 nm, and the emission spectrum was recorded at λ_{em} = 478- 750 nm.
- **Observations and conclusions:**

As SRh concentration increases, PN emission decreases with a slight deviation of 0.09 mM SRh, which is within the range of an error. The formation of the peak around 600 nm indicates the occurrence of energy transfer. The second graph shows that the highest intensity of SRh peak corresponds to 0.03 mM SRh.

Donor emission is significantly quenched in the coacervate state, whereas only slight quenching is observed in bulk solution, demonstrating that energy transfer requires close spatial confinement.

• **Data available at:**

"W:\AKDhiman\Team\Minea Kapidzic\Fluorescent spectroscopy\30092025_M-ET-17"

Relevant for the manuscript Figure S8, Figure S13, Figure S14, Figure S15, Figure S16, Figure 2 (a,b)

Attached files

et 17 sol vs co.png

sha256: fe217daafd7b1cf8ff902aeba9d6514bb7ad1e29fcb3031761af2a7c4066ba7e

et 17 sol.png

sha256: 16ff9bb4b1712e14c090643b54d3b160127ec4778a8fb41be15c4de4461b32fd

et 17.png

sha256: c196b10e5660113bf2ee76b1cfcd8e445168a141c51db247d6fa8f9df5e4d2bc

12.10 et18.png

sha256: abe3a168c4667f31b7f595a0f2829165622ebfdf6ef9a2fdf272a1a3b3cdc8db

Unique eLabID: 20251109-59cd4c40154e8f9067718730a72b6d59a133d8b0
Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=9151>

Aim: Energy transfer experiment via fluorescent spectroscopy

- **Materials and methods:** poly-L-lysine (Sigma Aldrich, average Mw=22500), pyranine (Carl Roth), Sulforhodamine B (Sigma Aldrich), MQ water
- **Sample preparation:** 50 mM SRh stock in MQ water was diluted to different concentrations (0.03, 0.06, 0.09, 0.12, and 0.15 mM). PLL stock solution was prepared (5 mM). To each SRh solution, PN (3 mM) and PLL (40 μ M) were added.
- **Instrumentation-**
 1. Spectra were recorded on a JASCO FP-800 fluorescence spectrometer. Samples were prepared as stated and measured in Quartz cuvettes (500 μ L Hellma Analytics) with a path length of 10x2 mm. The sample was excited at λ_{ex} = 458 nm, and the emission spectrum was recorded at λ_{em} = 478- 750 nm.
- **Observations and conclusions:**

As SRh concentration increases, PN emission decreases. The formation of the peak around 600 nm indicates the occurrence of energy transfer.

- **Data available at:**

"W:\AKDhiman\Team\Minea Kapidzic\Fluorescent spectroscopy\12102025_M-ET-18"

Relevant for the manuscript Figure S14.

Attached files

18.png

sha256: e63161be27836d9ac44aebff37c2b42f3309a52d89500bad6c841153ad4fb201

12.10 et18.png

sha256: abe3a168c4667f31b7f595a0f2829165622ebfdf6ef9a2fdf272a1a3b3cdc8db

Unique eLabID: 20251109-e23bb0bac06e10fc1edb9779c78232b14346c435
Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=9150>

Aim: Fluorescence Recovery After Photobleaching (FRAP) of PN-PLL coacervates using Cy5 dye to confirm liquid-like behavior.

Materials Required:

Milli-Q (MQ) water

Pyranine (PN) – Stock concentration: 100 mM

Poly-L-Lysine (PLL) – Stock concentration: 5 mM

Cy5 dye – 100 mM stock solution

Microscope slides with modified coverslips

Instrument Used: LEICA DMi 8 (Seiffert lab)

Procedure:

1. PN-PLL coacervate were prepared at 6 mM PN and 40 μ M PLL.
2. Cy5 dye was added to the coacervate solution.
3. 20 μ L of sample was added to the capillary channel on the glass slide, and FRAP was performed with an excitation wavelength of 631 nm.

Observation:

(a) CLSM images of PLL-PN coacervates obtained during FRAP, (b) Corresponding FRAP kinetics. [PN] = 6 mM, [PLL] = 40 μ M, [Cy5] = 0.02 mM. Scale bar = 5 μ m.

FRAP kinetics of PN-PLL coacervates at 3 mM PN and 6 mM PN with Cy5 dye (0.02 mM).

Result: The PN-PLL coacervates at 6 mM exhibit liquid-like nature, as evidenced by fluorescence recovery following photobleaching. However, when compared to 3 mM PN, 40 μ M PLL, the recovery is lower ($\approx 47\%$), which is around 10% lower compared to 3 mM PN, 40 μ M coacervates. Reduced mobility indicates a denser environment.

Relevant for manuscript Figure S6 and S7

Attached files

image.png

sha256: 3bfbabd0079daedd190e941738a3e0145e22c75e70da4366a7f6a07387cc3670

image.png

sha256: 3bfbabd0079daedd190e941738a3e0145e22c75e70da4366a7f6a07387cc3670

image.png

sha256: 8754dae80be647afaa084547f48ae837a0898257104ff194627a1fb77764d06f

Unique eLabID: 20260223-de6f30458a6fd8209db8011ef5541122b2c04c04

Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=20518>

Aim: Fluorescence Recovery After Photobleaching (FRAP) of ATP-PLL coacervates using Cy5 dye to confirm liquid-like behavior.

Materials Required:

Milli-Q (MQ) water

ATP - Stock concentration: 500 mM, pH=7.01

Poly-L-Lysine (PLL) - Stock concentration: 5 mM

Cy5 dye - 100 mM stock solution

Microscope slides with modified coverslips

Instrument Used: LEICA DMi 8 (Seiffert lab)

Procedure:

1. ATP-PLL coacervate were prepared at 5 mM ATP and 15 μ M PLL.
2. Cy5 dye was added to the coacervate solution.
3. 20 μ L of sample was added to the capillary channel on the glass slide, and FRAP was performed with an excitation wavelength of 631 nm.

Observation:

CLSM images of PLL-ATP coacervates obtained during FRAP. [ATP] = 5 mM, [PLL] = 15 μ M, [Cy5] = 0.02 mM. Scale bar = 5 μ m; kinetic profile

Result:

The PLL-ATP coacervates are highly liquid in nature. Coacervates recover rapidly, before the bleaching spot can be observed.

Relevant for manuscript Figure S9

Attached files

image.png
 sha256: 9e40b4694276804aff07b7085bb759e3b1394731c13109b40ec933a051b6bb05

image.png
 sha256: 6cdc5ddd9ebd72ea37d8847d53bc04cc28e720bb528729131c411d392d30b4d6

image.png
 sha256: 065befed175c4ae074e8ff6c7f83a65680b8c835f84924ef601d27d1a16e80db

Unique eLabID: 20260223-146b2464ee62d1b87b6a98784389bfff4be9a858
Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=20527>

Aim- Excitation spectrum of 3 mM PN in solution and in coacervate state

- **Materials and methods:** pyranin (Carl Roth), poly-L-lysine (Sigma-Aldrich), MQ water
- **Sample preparation:** A 3 mM PN solution was prepared from a 100 mM PN stock; coacervates were prepared as per standard procedure.
- **Instrumentation-**
 1. Spectra were recorded on a JASCO FP-800 fluorescence spectrometer. Samples were prepared as stated and measured in Quartz cuvettes (500 μ L Hellma Analytics) with a path length of 10 \times 2 mm. Spectra were recorded at λ_{em} =512 nm.
- **Observations and conclusions:**

Excitation spectra of 3 mM PN in solution and coacervate state at λ_{em} = 512 nm, showing a pronounced red shift upon coacervate formation.

Relevant for manuscript Figure S3

Attached file

image.png

sha256: 9219fb3042c50422976870d56d18701e2df6d8db741f87512d0e51266b52a5ac

Unique eLabID: 20260223-6055162ee60525bd8de150e82695add9e46f88c9

Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=20530>

Aim: Fluorescence Recovery After Photobleaching (FRAP) of PN-PLL coacervates using Cy5 dye to confirm liquid-like behavior.

Materials Required:

Milli-Q (MQ) water

Pyranine (PN) – Stock concentration: 100 mM

Poly-L-Lysine (PLL) – Stock concentration: 5 mM

Cy5 dye – 100 mM stock solution

Microscope slides with modified coverslips

Instrument Used: LEICA DMi 8 (Seiffert lab)

Procedure:

1. PN-PLL coacervate were prepared at 3 mM PN and 40 μ M PLL.
2. 0.1 μ L from 100 mM stock of Cy5 dye was added to the coacervate solution.
3. 20 μ L of sample was added to the capillary channel on the glass slide and FRAP was performed with an excitation wavelength of 631 nm.

Observation:

Scale bar = 5 μ m

Result: The PN-PLL coacervates exhibit liquid-like nature, as evidenced by fluorescence recovery following photobleaching.

Data: "C:\Users\mokumar\OneDrive - JGU\Experimental\Energy transfer project\CLSM Data\MK-ET-02"

"Y:\Team\Kumar Mohit\Energy transfer project\DATA\CLSM DATA\MK-ET-02"

FRAP 008, FRAP 007, FRAP 006 was used

Relevant for Figure 1 and S5

Attached file

image.png

sha256: e79c124590ace1ddb14dd712e8797c515eae9d89b6b4d110cf3bf7d429fd8e4a

Unique eLabID: 20251022-3ff4db2ab2851b2b989dc0c71209d64d37bceddb

Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=8877>

Aim: Determination of the partition coefficient of Pyranine (PN) and Sulforhodamine B (SRh) in PN-PLL coacervates.

Materials Required:

Milli-Q (MQ) water

Pyranine (PN) – Stock concentration: 5 mM

Poly-L-Lysine (PLL) – Stock concentration: 100 mM

Sulforhodamine B (SRh) – used at 0.03 mM of PN concentration

Instrument used: LEICA DMI8 (Seiffert lab)

Procedure:

1. PN-PLL coacervate was prepared at 3 mM PN and 40 μ M PLL.

For the calculation of the partition coefficient of PN, imaging was done at 458 nm excitation wavelength.

2. PN-PLL coacervate was prepared at 3 mM PN and 40 μ M PLL and 0.03 mM of SRh was added before formation of coacervates.

For the calculation of the partition coefficient of SRh, imaging was done at 561 nm excitation wavelength.

Partition coefficient was calculated using the formula: $K_p = (I_{\text{coacervate}} - I_{\text{blank}}) / (I_{\text{dilute phase}} - I_{\text{blank}})$

I_{blank} and $I_{\text{dilute phase}}$ was obtained using Image J and $I_{\text{coacervate}}$ was obtained using Python code available freely at : <https://github.com/Mokumar16/Intensity-calculation-of-coacervates.git>

Observation:

Result: PN and SRb partition preferentially into PN-PLL coacervates.

Data: "C:\Users\mokumar\OneDrive - JGU\Experimental\Energy transfer project\CLSM Data\MK-ET-03"

"Y:\Team\Kumar Mohit\Energy transfer project\DATA\CLSM DATA\MK-ET-03"

Relevant for Figure 1 and S11

Attached files

image.png

sha256: 63ced523e9122cb6b0bdf556125f42e5c64d9be4b187f3b9832f6c442951cfb8

image.png

sha256: 01d43ddef3952b605be1a83be47772a4361388bd276f554f3d9102d0c5af8d00

Unique eLabID: 20251022-080692d9dbf773484aae594c8a97a2cc325bd889

Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=8878>

Aim: Energy transfer analysis among PN and SRh in PLL-ATP coacervates

Materials Required:

Milli-Q (MQ) water

Pyranine (PN) - Stock concentration: 100 mM

Poly-L-Lysine (PLL) - Stock concentration: 5 mM

Sulforhodamine B (SRh) - used at 0.03 - 0.15 mol% of PN concentration

Instrument used: LEICA DMI8 (Seiffert lab)

Procedure:

1. PN-PLL coacervate was prepared at 3 mM PN and 40 μ M PLL.

To monitor the energy transfer, the sample was excited at 458 nm excitation wavelength.

2. SRh was added before the preparation of coacervates (0.03 - 0.15 mol% of PN concentration)

To calculate the intensity of PN and SRh channel python code was used available at:

1. Mokumar16/Dual-channel-intensity-calculation

<https://github.com/Mokumar16/Dual-channel-intensity-calculation>

Observation:

Figure 1: Plot of average fluorescence intensity of PN and SRh in PLL-PN coacervates extracted from CLSM images at different SRh concentrations (0-0.15 mM) $\lambda_{ex} = 458$ nm.

We observe decrease in PN emission on increasing concentration of SRh, which is due to energy transfer. SRh emission was increased till 0.06 mM after that we observed decrease in emission due to ACQ.

We quantified % Energy transfer using formula:

$$\Phi_{ET} = 1 - I_{DA} / I_D$$

where I_{DA} is the average fluorescence intensity of the donor within the coacervates in the presence of the acceptor, and I_D is the corresponding average donor intensity in the absence of the acceptor.

Figure 2: Comparison of percentage energy transfer at 0.03 and 0.06 mM SRh.

Figure 3: (a) CLSM images of PLL-ATP coacervates encapsulating SRh under indirect excitation at $\lambda_{ex} = 458$ nm showing no SRh emission, indicating the absence of energy transfer in the absence of PN (b) CLSM images under direct excitation of SRh $\lambda_{ex} = 561$ nm showing characteristic SRh emission. Green channel = PN, Red channel = SRh. [SRh] = 0.06 mM, Scale bar = 20 μ m.

The experiment was done 2 times and average is reported of set 1 and set 2.

Result: PN and SRh were showing energy transfer in coacervates.

Data: "C:\Users\mokumar\OneDrive - JGU\Experimental\Energy transfer project\CLSM Data\MK-ET-04"

"Y:\Team\Kumar Mohit\Energy transfer project\DATA\CLSM DATA\MK-ET-04"

Relevant for figure 2, S17

Attached files

image.png

sha256: 32e63ab83dff589095eea315f3e1670b4e2a0b1c7e117f5382dbfe42aca2df1e

image.png

sha256: 5c722277d45f7e1a8d3c755c9e80cfa8484aeb6c77ef10ef384a2a507ddeaf79

image.png

sha256: ccc34d64b6c4ffd1d51a2c351718a93e0f3216e0ed76c5ef81c30d77b7e9a101

Unique eLabID: 20251103-bc0e41c492304d723c92865a56b0896e79727fd5
Link: <http://elabftw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=9052>

Aim: Control experiment to prove no direct excitation at 458 nm of Sulphorhodamine B in CLSM.

Materials Required:

Milli-Q (MQ) water

ATP: 100 mM

Poly-L-Lysine (PLL) – Stock concentration: 5 mM

Sulforhodamine B – used at 0.06 mM.

Instrument used: LEICA DMI8 (Seiffert lab)

Procedure:

1. PLL-ATP coacervate was prepared at 5 mM ATP and 15 μ M PLL in MQ water.
- 2: SRh was added before the preparation of coacervates (final concentration 0.06 mM)

The coacervates were imaged in a confocal microscope using a 458 nm laser. For the Sulphorhodamine B channel, the gain was adjusted from 625 nm to 750 nm.

Observation:

Figure 1: (a) CLSM images of PLL-ATP coacervates encapsulating Sulphorhodamine B under indirect excitation at $\lambda_{ex} = 458$ nm showing no Sulphorhodamine B emission, indicating the absence of energy transfer in the absence of Pyranine. (b) CLSM images under direct excitation of Sulphorhodamine B $\lambda_{ex} = 561$ nm showing characteristic Sulphorhodamine B emission. Green channel = Pyranine, Red channel = Sulphorhodamine B. [Sulphorhodamine B] = 0.03 mM, Scale bar = 20 μ m.

We did not observe any fluorescence in the Pyranine and sulphorhodamine B channels at 458 nm.

Direct excitation at 561 nm shows the presence of sulphorhodamine B in coacervates.

Observation: No direct excitation of Sulphorhodamine B at 458 nm.

Result: No direct excitation of Sulphorhodamine B at 458 nm.

Data: "C:\Users\mokumar\OneDrive - JGU\Experimental\Energy transfer project\CLSM Data\MK-ET-05"

"Y:\Team\Kumar Mohit\Energy transfer project\DATA\CLSM DATA\MK-ET-05"

Relevant for figure S18

Attached file

image.png

sha256: eb708679a41374ea4231fce6bc50223ac2bc126bf24a1a9089fd670d1a783d48

Unique eLabID: 20251104-de0e9610f64c5a7d81e818d08db091f87c56297c

Link: <http://elabfw.biologie.uni-mainz.de/experiments.php?mode=view&id=9102>